

Critical Micelle Concentrations of Sulphonated Phenyl-, Toly-, and Xylyl-stearic Acids by Conductometric and pH-metric Measurements

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A comparative study has been made of the c.m.c. values of alkyl aryl sulphonic acids as obtained from polarographic data with those found by conductometric and pH-metric methods. Although the c.m.c. values have been found of the order $10^{-5}M$ by all the three methods, pH-metric and conductometric studies further show that the values increase with increase in chain length. The c.m.c. values have been found to be appreciably influenced by the presence of foreign electrolytes used in the polarographic method.

In an earlier communication¹, the results of c.m.c. values of sulphonated phenyl-, toly-, and xylyl-stearic acids, obtained by suppressing the polarographic maxima of different metal and complex ions, were reported. Since the data reported earlier¹ referred to c.m.c. values in presence of foreign ions (used for polarographic reduction), it was thought worthwhile to employ other methods for their determination. The conductometric method, although quite convenient for carrying out such determinations, could not provide c.m.c. values in presence of foreign electrolytes. The feasibility of employing the pH-metric method for this purpose was therefore considered.

Assuming that in dilute solutions of the soaps, under study, hydrogen ions would be released due to hydrolysis or ionisation, gradual dilution would result in a change of pH. When colloidal micelles start forming, the variations should, however, be much smaller than before and a break is observed near about the c.m.c. value. On these considerations, the use of pH-metric method was made to determine the c.m.c. values of these soaps both in presence and in absence of foreign ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The three soaps were prepared according to Stirton *et al.*². The solutions of different concentrations were prepared after diluting with double distilled water (all-glass). The pH and the conductance were determined with a Cambridge pH-meter and a Kohlrausch Universal Bridge, respectively, at 25°. The pHs of the soap solutions were also measured with the help of the hydrogen electrode. Almost concordant values of pH were obtained in both cases. Electrolytes used were of the A. R. quality and their solutions were also prepared in double distilled water.

1. Malik and Haque, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 35.
2. *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1940, 32, 1136.

TABLE I

Variation in the pH of HCl (pH 2.8) on addition of increasing amounts of soap and water respectively.

Volume of HCl.	*Volume of SPSA ($10^{-3}M$).	pH with	
		Soap.	Water.
14.0 ml	1.0 ml	2.81	2.89
13.0	2.0	2.81	2.91
12.0	3.0	2.81	2.93
10.0	5.0	2.81	3.01
8.0	7.0	2.81	3.12
5.0	10.0	2.82	3.30

*Refers to two different sets: one with SPSA and the other with double distilled water.

DISCUSSION

The behaviour of these soaps in aqueous medium is quite interesting. On the addition of 1ml of $10^{-3}M$ soap in 25 ml of double distilled water, a considerable decrease in pH has been observed, indicating thereby that the soap, which existed in the form of either molecular or in ionic micelles, starts ionising and behaves as a strong electrolyte:

On further addition of the soap, this decrease is maintained due to larger accumulation of hydrogen ions although a regular decrease, as observed with dilute solutions, ceases to exist. After a certain stage, further addition of the soap does not result in any change in pH. The concentration corresponding to this pH may be taken as the critical micelle concentration beyond which micelles start forming and the hydrogen ions present therein, instead of decreasing the pH, distribute themselves around the micelles, forming a kind of diffused double layer. Confirmation of this view has been obtained on noting the pH of the soap solution in HCl at pH 2.8 (the minimum pH realised) and the pH of the solutions obtained by diluting HCl with equivalent volumes of water (Table I).

The hyperbolic curves, obtained on plotting concentration vs. $\Delta\text{pH}/\Delta c$ (where ΔpH and Δc are the differences in the two successive pH readings and concentration respectively), could not provide accurate c.m.c. values. Accurate values could, however, be obtained on plotting $1/c$ vs. pH, when an abrupt change in pH with change in concentration was observed (typical curves with and without electrolytes are shown in Fig. 1).

On plotting specific conductance vs. concentration or molar conductance against square root of concentration, curves of the usual shape are obtained (Fig. 2). The values

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FIG. 1
 1—SPSA, scale A. 2—SPSA + Ni^{2+} in KCl, scale B.
 3—SPSA + Pb^{2+} in KNO_3 , scale C. 4—SPSA + CdI in KI, scale B.

FIG. 2
 1—Sp. conduc. vs. conc. 2—Molar conduc. vs. $\sqrt{c}$.

of c.m.c. obtained by this method together with those obtained from the polarographic and pH-metric methods are recorded in Table II.

Table II shows the following interesting points: (i) The order of c.m.c. values is $10^{-5}M$ both by the pH-metric and conductometric methods. This order also exists in most of the cases studied polarographically. (ii) Both with the pH-metric and conductometric methods, the c.m.c. values increase with increase in the chain length: this behaviour is not observed in the case of polarographic data. (iii) The c.m.c. values are appreciably influenced by the presence of foreign electrolytes in the soap solutions. It is obvious both from the values obtained from polarographic and pH-metric methods although the change is more marked by the former method.

TABLE II

Comparative c. m. c. values of SPSA, STSA, and SXSA from different electrochemical methods.

Ion or complex.	Critical micelle concentration (order $10^{-5}M$).								
	Polarographic†.			pH metric.			Conductometric.		
	SPSA.	STSA.	SXSA.	SPSA.	STSA.	SXSA.	SPSA.	STSA.	SXSA.
Without electrolyte	..	..	..	13.8	15.6	20.0	36.4	41.7	46.1
Ni ²⁺ in KCl	8.2	48.98	36.31	16.7	13.8	16.1	..	..	..
Pb ²⁺ in KNO ₃	9.8	2.19	1.29	16.0	16.7	17.8	..	..	..
Cd-iodine complex in KI	121.0	7.94	5.37	23.8	23.8	26.3	..	..	..

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